

INDICATORS THE DYNAMIC OF THE GERMINATION OF THE WHEAT SPROUTED FROM PLANT

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Relavance. Our republic has a population of grain and bread products to the needs of the growth of the grain to produce to increase and its quality increase requires will. The world 's population the most part present at the time less from eating suffer suffer. In children with protein failure is the lack of the developing countries the most important problems is one. This problem solve to for high oqsilli of grain cultivation, nutritional quality to improve particular attention focus should, because these crops are cheap, and protein of the substance as it is available. Triticale this need to satisfy to ability to have new grain crops is. This with in conjunction with today's day, the population of livestock to cost the requirement each time you grow up has been. High and quality of grain yield of the formation of very many factors, including, ekilayotgan varieties of genetic properties, soil-climate conditions, o'tmishdosh crops, feeding and watering regime related is. From year to year the population number increased may go for the reason flour and him ready term for the product, the demand is incredibly increased has.

RESULTS. As it is known, plant growth when you say, her in which the body at the expense strictly look at the plant mass increase, development is about , while, the plant organogenezi period navbatlashib that was consider should. Grain crops growth and development in the following proportions be can:

1. Fast growth, slow development-it leaves and root of the mass growth is taking place , giving generativ body is formed to be slightly delayed and the harvest of the mass of the little grain is. Slow growth and fast development of this plant to grow and will remain, enough root, leaf mass, organic substances, less is, however organogenez stages quickly will pass, as a result, the mass less of the spike , the appearance is , and the yield is reduced. Fast growth, rapid development in the leaf of the plate surface and the plant mass and organogenez stages between normal ratio formed is. Just like in the ratio of the plants in the grain and the stem between equal ratios of mass of the form it comes in. Slow growth and slow development - this plant has many of the mass formed be, they are late ripening is reached. Grain crops growth and development track to go all the technological means of rational use as a result of the plants for favorable conditions create should.

Grain crops o'suv period of multiple phenological period over detected. Each is a period of the structure, appearance and the quality in all respects from each other by different makes. Grain crops following phenological periods identified: maysalanish, tuplanish, stem wrap, boshoplanish (ro'vaklash), flowering and ripening. Each one a new era into 10% of the plant that had passed if it is determined, then this period the plant is full of the last that is. Development period of the exchange in the plant of the new organ the appearance to be with , is characterized.

Conclusion. The place can you say that in conclusion, this indicator tritikale control of “Nutritious” in varieties of 1-in option out of the lawn, the number of sprouts per day come October 18, 30 %, on October 20, 51 %, 36 on October 22 %, 24 October a day for 75 %, on October 26 88 % if it was up to the 2-in option “Sardor” October 18 varieties of 28 %, on 20 October 485 %, on October 22 61 %, October 24 to 72 %, 85 on October 26 % equaled. Again also “Guldu” varieties in 1-option in the grass in the number of sprouts coming out October 18, 34 %, on 20 October to 53% on October 22 of 65 %, October 24 to 77 %, 91 on October 26 %, was stressed.

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